

Personal Competencies and Work Engagement Among Muslim Women Executives in Tawi-Tawi

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Abstract. The effectiveness of organizational leadership is increasingly associated with leaders' personal competencies and their ability to foster positive workplace attitudes and behaviors. This study examined the personal competencies and work engagement of Muslim women executives in Tawi-Tawi. Specifically, it determined the level of personal competencies in terms of communication, integrity, stress management, and personal engagement; assessed employee work engagement based on vigor, dedication, and absorption; determined differences in personal competencies and work engagement when respondents were grouped according to profile variables; and examined the relationship between personal competencies and employee work engagement. The study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design involving 24 Muslim women executives and 120 subordinates from selected government agencies and institutions in Tawi-Tawi. Data were collected using validated survey instruments and analyzed using frequency counts, percentages, means, standard deviations, Mann-Whitney U Test, Kruskal-Wallis H Test, and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation. Findings revealed that Muslim women executives demonstrated a proficient level of personal competencies and a very high level of work engagement. Communication emerged as the highest-rated competency dimension, while vigor obtained the highest rating among work engagement dimensions. Statistical analyses indicated no significant differences in personal competencies and work engagement across selected profile variables. Furthermore, the relationship between personal competencies and employee work engagement was found to be statistically insignificant. The findings suggest that Muslim women executives possess strong personal competencies and maintain high levels of engagement regardless of demographic and professional characteristics. The study highlights the importance of sustaining leadership development programs that strengthen communication, integrity, stress management, and personal engagement among women leaders.

Keywords: Employee Engagement; Leadership; Muslim Women Executives; Personal Competencies; Work Engagement

Introduction

The contemporary workplace increasingly recognizes the critical role of leadership competencies in achieving organizational effectiveness and sustainable performance. In both public and private organizations, executives are expected not only to possess technical and managerial expertise but also to demonstrate strong personal competencies that enable them to navigate complex organizational environments. Personal competencies encompass the behavioral, emotional, and interpersonal attributes

that contribute to effective leadership, including communication, integrity, stress management, and personal engagement. These competencies are essential for fostering productive work environments, enhancing employee motivation, and promoting organizational success.

Employee work engagement has emerged as one of the most important indicators of organizational effectiveness. According to Schaufeli et al. (2020), work engagement is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption, reflecting employees' positive, fulfilling, and work-related state of mind. Engaged employees demonstrate higher productivity, stronger commitment, lower turnover intentions, and greater organizational citizenship behaviors. Consequently, understanding factors that contribute to work engagement has become a major concern among scholars and practitioners alike.

Among leadership populations, Muslim women executives represent a unique and increasingly influential group. In many societies, Muslim women continue to navigate cultural expectations, organizational demands, and leadership responsibilities simultaneously. Despite these challenges, recent studies indicate that Muslim women leaders contribute significantly to organizational development through transformational leadership practices, ethical decision-making, and effective stakeholder engagement (Metcalf & Rees, 2021). Their leadership experiences provide valuable insights into the relationship between personal competencies and workplace outcomes.

The Province of Tawi-Tawi, located within the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), presents a distinct sociocultural and administrative context for examining women's leadership. As government agencies and institutions continue to promote gender inclusivity and leadership development, Muslim women increasingly occupy executive and managerial positions. However, empirical studies examining their personal competencies and work engagement remain limited. Existing literature has primarily focused on leadership barriers, gender issues, and organizational challenges, leaving a significant gap regarding the competencies and engagement levels of Muslim women executives in the region.

Although leadership competencies and employee work engagement have been extensively examined in organizational and management literature, existing studies have predominantly focused on Western settings, mixed-gender leadership populations, or general managerial groups. Limited empirical evidence is available on Muslim women executives, particularly within culturally distinct and geographically marginalized regions such as Tawi-Tawi in the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). Previous research has largely emphasized gender-related barriers, leadership challenges, and socio-cultural constraints faced by Muslim women, while insufficient attention has been given to their personal competencies and their potential influence on employee work engagement. Moreover, the relationship between communication, integrity, stress management, and personal engagement and the work engagement dimensions of vigor, dedication, and absorption remains underexplored in Islamic and multicultural organizational contexts. This gap limits the understanding of how Muslim women executives contribute to organizational effectiveness and employee outcomes. Therefore, this study investigates the personal competencies and employee work engagement of Muslim women executives in Tawi-Tawi to provide context-specific evidence and contribute to the growing body of knowledge on leadership, employee engagement, and women's leadership in Muslim-majority settings as well as the organizational behavior in multicultural and Islamic contexts.

Research Questions

This study sought to determine the personal competencies and work engagement of Muslim women executives in the Province of Tawi-Tawi. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of Muslim women executives in terms of age, position, educational attainment, administrative experience, employment status, and eligibility?
2. What is the level of personal competencies of Muslim women executives in terms of: a) Stress Management; b) Integrity; c) Communication; and d) Personal Engagement?
3. What is the level of employee work engagement in terms of: a) Absorption; b) Dedication; and c). Vigor?
4. Are there significant differences in personal competencies and work engagement when respondents are grouped according to profile variables?

5. Is there a significant relationship between personal competencies and employee work engagement?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focused on examining the personal competencies and employee work engagement among Muslim women executives in the Province of Tawi-Tawi, Philippines. Specifically, the study assessed the level of personal competencies in terms of communication, integrity, stress management, and personal engagement, and determined the level of employee work engagement based on vigor, dedication, and absorption. It also investigated whether significant differences existed in personal competencies and work engagement when respondents were grouped according to selected demographic and professional characteristics, namely age, current position, highest educational attainment, administrative work experience, employment status, and eligibility. Furthermore, the study examined the relationship between personal competencies and employee work engagement. The study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. The respondents consisted of twenty-four (24) Muslim women executives occupying leadership and managerial positions in selected government agencies and institutions in the Province of Tawi-Tawi and one hundred twenty (120) subordinates who provided supplementary assessments of the executives' competencies and engagement. Data were gathered through a structured survey questionnaire adapted from established competency and work engagement frameworks and were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques, including mean, standard deviation, Mann-Whitney U Test, Kruskal-Wallis H Test, and Spearman Rank-Order Correlation. The study was delimited to Muslim women executives serving in selected public sector organizations within Tawi-Tawi during the conduct of the research. It did not include male executives, non-Muslim women executives, private sector managers, or leaders from other provinces within the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). Likewise, the study focused exclusively on four dimensions of personal competencies, communication, integrity, stress management, and personal engagement—and three dimensions of work engagement—vigor, dedication, and absorption. Other leadership competencies, organizational factors, psychological variables, and environmental influences that may affect work engagement, such as organizational culture, job satisfaction, leadership style, motivation, compensation, and institutional support, were beyond the scope of the investigation. The findings of this study are therefore limited to the respondents included in the research and may not be generalized to all Muslim women executives in the Philippines or other organizational settings. Nevertheless, the results provide valuable empirical evidence regarding the competencies and work engagement of Muslim women executives in Tawi-Tawi and contribute to the growing body of literature on women's leadership, organizational behavior, and public sector management within the Bangsamoro context.

Literature Review

Personal Competencies

Personal competencies have long been recognized as an important determinant of leadership effectiveness. Beyond technical expertise and formal qualifications, leaders are expected to possess personal attributes that enable them to work effectively with others, make sound decisions, and respond appropriately to organizational challenges. These competencies influence how leaders interact with employees, address workplace issues, and contribute to organizational goals. Boyatzis (2018) described competencies as underlying characteristics that distinguish highly effective performers from those with average levels of performance. In leadership settings, competencies are often reflected through communication practices, ethical conduct, emotional regulation, and commitment to work. For women occupying executive positions, personal competencies become particularly important because leadership responsibilities frequently require balancing organizational demands with interpersonal expectations. The ability to communicate effectively, maintain integrity, manage stress, and remain engaged in one's role contributes significantly to leadership success and organizational effectiveness (Northouse, 2022).

Communication

Communication remains one of the most frequently cited characteristics of successful leaders. It serves as the primary means through which leaders share information, communicate expectations, provide direction, and establish relationships with employees. Effective communication promotes understanding, minimizes misunderstandings, and encourages collaboration within organizations. Men (2021) emphasized that communication is not limited to the transmission of information but also involves active listening, empathy, and meaningful interaction with employees. Leaders who communicate openly are more likely to gain the trust of their subordinates and foster a positive work environment. When employees clearly understand organizational goals and expectations, they tend to become more committed to their work and more willing to contribute to organizational success. In public organizations, where coordination among various stakeholders is essential, communication competency becomes even more critical. Leaders who communicate clearly and consistently are better positioned to manage organizational change, resolve conflicts, and maintain employee morale.

Integrity

Integrity is widely regarded as one of the most essential qualities of effective leadership. It refers to honesty, consistency, accountability, and adherence to ethical standards. Employees often evaluate leaders not only by what they say but also by whether their actions align with their stated values and commitments. Brown and Treviño (2019) argued that integrity serves as the foundation of ethical leadership because it strengthens trust between leaders and followers. When employees perceive their leaders as honest and fair, they are more likely to demonstrate commitment, cooperation, and confidence in organizational decisions. Conversely, the absence of integrity can weaken trust and negatively affect organizational relationships. Within government institutions, integrity is particularly important because public officials are expected to uphold transparency, accountability, and public trust. Leaders who consistently demonstrate ethical behavior contribute to a workplace culture that values responsibility and professionalism.

Stress Management

Leadership positions inevitably involve pressure. Executives are expected to make critical decisions, address organizational problems, manage personnel concerns, and respond to changing workplace demands. Consequently, the ability to manage stress effectively is an important leadership competency. Quick and Henderson (2016) noted that stress itself is not always harmful; rather, difficulties arise when individuals lack the coping mechanisms necessary to manage workplace pressures. Leaders who can regulate their emotions and maintain composure during challenging situations are often better equipped to make rational decisions and provide stability within their organizations. Stress management is particularly relevant in contemporary workplaces characterized by rapid change, increasing workloads, and growing expectations for organizational performance. Leaders who effectively manage stress tend to demonstrate greater resilience and adaptability, qualities that are increasingly valued in today's organizational environment.

Personal Engagement

Personal engagement reflects the extent to which individuals invest themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally in their work. Kahn (1990) described engagement as the process through which people bring their full selves into the performance of their roles. Leaders who are personally engaged often display enthusiasm, commitment, and a genuine interest in organizational success. Their involvement tends to influence the attitudes and behaviors of employees, creating a work environment where commitment and motivation are encouraged. Bakker and Albrecht (2018) observed that engaged leaders are more likely to foster positive workplace relationships and contribute to a culture of productivity and collaboration. Personal engagement is particularly important among executives because leadership effectiveness often depends on the ability to inspire and motivate others. Employees are more likely to respond positively when they perceive their leaders as genuinely invested in the organization and its goals.

Employee Work Engagement

Work engagement has received considerable attention in organizational research because of its association with positive workplace outcomes. Unlike burnout, which is characterized by exhaustion and detachment, work engagement reflects a positive psychological state marked by energy, involvement, and enthusiasm toward work. Schaufeli et al. (2020) conceptualized work engagement through three dimensions: vigor, dedication, and absorption. Together, these dimensions capture the extent to which employees are energized by their work, committed to their responsibilities, and fully immersed in their tasks. Organizations increasingly recognize work engagement as a valuable resource because engaged employees tend to perform better, demonstrate stronger commitment, and contribute positively to organizational goals. High levels of engagement have also been linked to improved employee well-being, productivity, and job satisfaction.

Vigor

Vigor refers to high levels of energy, persistence, and mental resilience while performing work tasks. Employees who exhibit vigor are willing to invest considerable effort in their work and remain persistent even when confronted with challenges or setbacks (Schaufeli et al., 2020). Research suggests that vigor contributes significantly to individual and organizational performance because energetic employees tend to approach tasks proactively and maintain productivity despite workplace pressures. Vigor has also been associated with psychological well-being, resilience, and job satisfaction, making it an important dimension of work engagement (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018).

Dedication

Dedication reflects a strong sense of involvement in work accompanied by enthusiasm, pride, inspiration, and a perception that one's work is meaningful. Employees who demonstrate dedication often feel emotionally connected to their responsibilities and organizational objectives (Schaufeli et al., 2020). Dedication contributes to organizational commitment because employees become emotionally connected to their responsibilities and organizational objectives. As a result, they are more likely to remain motivated and committed even when confronted with workplace difficulties. Dedication fosters a sense of purpose that motivates employees to persist in achieving organizational goals even when confronted with challenges (Bakker & Albrecht, 2018).

Absorption

Absorption refers to being fully concentrated and deeply immersed in work activities. Employees experiencing absorption often become so involved in their tasks that they lose track of time and find it difficult to disengage from their work. This dimension reflects a high level of psychological involvement in work and is frequently associated with increased productivity and task accomplishment. Employees who are absorbed in their work often experience a sense of enjoyment and fulfillment that further strengthens engagement.

Relationship Between Personal Competencies and Work Engagement

The connection between leadership competencies and employee work engagement has become an important area of inquiry in organizational research. Leaders influence employee attitudes not only through formal authority but also through their personal behaviors, interpersonal skills, and ability to create supportive work environments. When leaders communicate effectively, demonstrate integrity, manage stress constructively, and remain engaged in their responsibilities, employees are more likely to perceive their workplace positively. Such perceptions can foster trust, commitment, and a greater willingness to invest effort in work-related activities. Consequently, personal competencies are often viewed as important factors that contribute to employee engagement and organizational effectiveness. Within the context of Muslim women executives, examining this relationship provides valuable insights into how leadership competencies shape workplace experiences in culturally diverse and public-sector settings. As more Muslim women assume leadership roles, understanding the factors associated with effective leadership and employee engagement becomes increasingly relevant to both organizational practice and academic scholarship. This study is anchored on the Competency Theory of Boyatzis (2018), which posits that

effective performance is influenced by competencies that integrate knowledge, skills, and behavioral attributes. The study is likewise supported by the Work Engagement Theory of Schaufeli et al. (2020), which conceptualizes engagement through vigor, dedication, and absorption. The framework assumes that higher levels of personal competencies among Muslim women executives contribute to higher levels of employee work engagement. Although previous studies have consistently emphasized the importance of communication, integrity, stress management, and personal engagement in enhancing leadership effectiveness (Men, 2021; Northouse, 2022; Bakker & Albrecht, 2018), most investigations were conducted in Western, corporate, or mixed-gender settings. Similarly, research on work engagement has established that vigor, dedication, and absorption contribute positively to employee performance and organizational outcomes (Schaufeli et al., 2020). These studies collectively suggest that leaders' competencies may influence employees' attitudes and engagement at work. However, findings remain inconclusive regarding how these relationships operate within culturally distinct environments and among underrepresented leadership groups such as Muslim women executives. Existing studies on Muslim women leaders have primarily focused on gender barriers, cultural expectations, and leadership challenges rather than examining their personal competencies and their association with employee work engagement. Moreover, little empirical evidence exists within the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), particularly in Tawi-Tawi, where leadership is shaped by unique cultural, religious, and organizational contexts. Consequently, it remains unclear whether the competency-engagement relationships reported in previous studies are applicable in this setting. By examining the personal competencies of Muslim women executives and their relationship with employee work engagement, the present study extends existing literature, provides context-specific evidence from an underrepresented population, and addresses a significant gap in leadership and organizational behavior research.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design to examine the relationship between personal competencies and employee work engagement among Muslim women in the Province of Tawi-Tawi. The quantitative approach was utilized because it allows for the collection and analysis of numerical data to objectively describe the variables and determine the extent of their relationship through statistical procedures (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The descriptive component of the study was used to determine the level of personal competencies in terms of communication, integrity, stress management, and personal engagement, as well as the level of employee work engagement in terms of vigor, dedication, and absorption. This approach provided a comprehensive description of the respondents' competencies and engagement within their respective organizational settings (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The correlational component was employed to determine whether a significant relationship exists between personal competencies and employee work engagement. Specifically, the study examined the extent to which communication, integrity, stress management, and personal engagement are associated with employees' vigor, dedication, and absorption. Correlational research is appropriate when investigating the degree and direction of relationships among variables without manipulating them (Fraenkel et al., 2019). The study was anchored on Competency Theory developed by Boyatzis (1982), which posits that effective performance is influenced by a combination of personal characteristics, skills, knowledge, and behaviors that enable individuals to perform successfully in their roles. The theory suggests that leaders and employees who possess strong competencies are more likely to achieve higher levels of effectiveness and organizational performance. The study was likewise grounded on the Work Engagement Theory of Schaufeli and Bakker (2004), which conceptualizes work engagement as a positive and fulfilling work-related state characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption. According to the theory, engaged employees demonstrate high levels of energy, commitment, and involvement in their work, resulting in improved individual and organizational outcomes. Furthermore, the study adopted a non-experimental design, as the variables were examined in their natural setting without manipulation or intervention. This design enabled the researcher to investigate the relationship between personal competencies and employee work engagement as they naturally occur among Muslim women in the Province of Tawi-Tawi (Fraenkel et

al., 2019). Overall, the quantitative descriptive-correlational design was deemed appropriate because it provided a systematic and empirical framework for describing the respondents' personal competencies and work engagement and for determining the relationship between these variables.

Sampling Design

This study employed purposive sampling in selecting the respondents. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling technique in which participants are selected based on specific characteristics relevant to the objectives of the study (Etikan & Bala, 2017). Purposive sampling was deemed appropriate because it enabled the researcher to obtain relevant and reliable data from individuals who possess firsthand knowledge and experience related to personal competencies and employee work engagement (Campbell et al., 2020).

Research Locale

This study was conducted in the Province of Tawi-Tawi, one of the island provinces of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), located in the southernmost part of the Philippines. Tawi-Tawi is composed of several municipalities characterized by cultural diversity, a predominantly Muslim population, and a unique socio-political environment that reflects the rich heritage of the Bangsamoro people. The study focused on selected government agencies and public institutions within the province where Muslim women occupy executive, managerial, supervisory, and leadership positions. These institutions serve as important venues for examining leadership practices, personal competencies, and employee work engagement among Muslim women in public service. Tawi-Tawi was chosen as the research locale because of the increasing participation of Muslim women in leadership and decision-making roles within government organizations. Despite their growing representation in executive positions, limited empirical studies have examined the relationship between personal competencies and employee work engagement among Muslim women leaders in the province. As such, the locale provides a relevant context for investigating leadership competencies and workplace engagement within a culturally distinct and geographically unique setting.

Research Participants

The participants of this study consisted of 24 Muslim women executives and 120 subordinate employees from selected government agencies and public institutions in the Province of Tawi-Tawi, Philippines. The Muslim women executives served as the primary respondents, while the subordinate employees provided supplementary assessments to enrich and validate the findings related to personal competencies and work engagement. The executive participants were selected using purposive sampling based on the following inclusion criteria: (a) Muslim women currently occupying executive, managerial, supervisory, or other leadership positions; (b) employed in government agencies or public institutions within the Province of Tawi-Tawi; (c) possessing at least one year of administrative or leadership experience; and (d) willing to participate voluntarily in the study. These participants were deemed appropriate because of their direct involvement in organizational leadership, decision-making, and employee supervision. To obtain a more comprehensive assessment of leadership competencies and employee work engagement, 120 subordinates directly supervised by the participating executives were also included in the study. The subordinate participants met the following criteria: (a) currently employed in the same organization as the participating executive; (b) directly reporting to or working under the supervision of the identified Muslim woman executive; (c) having rendered at least six months of service in the organization; and (d) willing to participate voluntarily in the study. The inclusion of both Muslim women executives and their subordinates provided multiple perspectives on personal competencies and work engagement. While the executives provided self-assessments of their competencies and engagement, subordinate employees offered complementary evaluations based on their direct working relationships with the executives. This multi-source approach enhanced the credibility and validity of the findings by integrating both self-reported and subordinate-rated data, thereby providing a more comprehensive understanding of the relationship between personal competencies and employee work engagement among Muslim women executives in the Province of Tawi-Tawi.

Research Instrument

This study utilized a structured questionnaire as the primary data-gathering instrument. The instrument consisted of three parts: (1) respondents' profile, (2) personal competencies, and (3) employee work engagement. The Personal Competencies Scale measured four dimensions: stress management, integrity, communication, and personal engagement. While the Employee Work Engagement Scale measured three dimensions: absorption, dedication, and vigor, based on the framework of Schaufeli and Bakker (2004). A five-point Likert scale was used to measure the respondents' perceptions, with responses ranging from 5 (Very High) to 1 (Very Low). Higher scores indicated higher levels of personal competencies and work engagement. Prior to data collection, the instrument was subjected to expert validation to ensure content validity and was pilot-tested to establish reliability. Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to determine internal consistency, with a reliability coefficient of 0.70 or higher considered acceptable (Taber, 2018).

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first secured approval from the Graduate School and obtained permission from the heads of the participating government agencies and institutions in the Province of Tawi-Tawi. Upon approval, the researcher coordinated with designated focal persons to identify eligible participants based on the established inclusion criteria. The purpose of the study was explained to the participants, and informed consent was obtained before data collection. Copies of the survey questionnaire were personally distributed to the Muslim women executives and their subordinates. Participants were given sufficient time to complete the instrument and were assured that their responses would be treated with strict confidentiality and used solely for academic purposes. Completed questionnaires were retrieved, checked for completeness, coded, and organized for statistical analysis. The collected data were then encoded into the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for processing and interpretation. The following statistical tools were utilized in analyzing the data: 1) Frequency Counts and Percentages. These were used to describe the demographic profile of the participants; 2) Mean and Standard Deviation. These were employed to determine the level of personal competencies and employee work engagement; 3) Mann-Whitney U Test. This nonparametric test was used to determine significant differences between two independent groups. The null hypothesis was rejected when the p-value was less than 0.05; 4) Kruskal-Wallis H Test. This test was used to determine significant differences among three or more independent groups. The null hypothesis was rejected when the p-value was less than 0.05; and 5) Spearman Rank-Order Correlation (Spearman's rho). This test was employed to determine the relationship between personal competencies and employee work engagement. Correlation coefficients were interpreted as follows: 0.00–0.19 (very weak), 0.20–0.39 (weak), 0.40–0.59 (moderate), 0.60–0.79 (strong), and 0.80–1.00 (very strong). The relationship was considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What is the profile of Muslim women executives in terms of age, position, educational attainment, administrative experience, employment status, and eligibility?

Table 1. MWE Profile, N=24

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	5.92	0.881
Current Position	1.67	0.761
Highest Educational Attainment	2.92	0.881
Admin. Work Experience	2.08	1.316
Employment Status	1.83	0.963
Eligibility	1.42	0.654
Average	2.64	0.909

As shown in Table 1, the Muslim women executives obtained an overall mean of 2.64 (SD = 0.91), indicating variation in their age, position, educational attainment, administrative work experience, employment status, and eligibility. Among the profile variables, age registered the highest mean (M = 5.92, SD = 0.88), suggesting that most respondents were in the mature stage of their careers and had accumulated substantial professional and leadership experience (Northouse, 2022). The respondents also exhibited relatively high educational qualifications, with highest educational attainment obtaining a mean of 2.92 (SD = 0.88), indicating that many had pursued advanced academic studies that may have enhanced their leadership and managerial competencies (Boyatzis, 2018). Likewise, the results for administrative work experience (M = 2.08, SD = 1.32), current position (M = 1.67, SD = 0.76), employment status (M = 1.83, SD = 0.96), and eligibility (M = 1.42, SD = 0.65) reflect a diverse group of executives with varying professional backgrounds and leadership responsibilities. Overall, the findings suggest that the respondents were experienced and academically qualified leaders, providing a strong foundation for examining personal competencies and employee work engagement among Muslim women executives in Tawi-Tawi.

Table 2. Subordinate's Profile, N120

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
Age	2.3167	1.32198
Current Position	1.6333	0.77712
Highest Educational Attainment	1.2583	0.47626
Admin Work Experience	1.2583	0.43955
Employment Status	1.7167	0.87143
Eligibility	1.2000	0.44154
Average	1.5639	0.7213

Table 2 presents the profile of the subordinate respondents, which yielded an overall mean of 1.56 (SD = 0.72), indicating a diverse representation of employees across demographic and professional characteristics. Among the profile variables, age obtained the highest mean (M = 2.32, SD = 1.32), suggesting that respondents came from various age groups and brought different workplace experiences and perspectives to the study. The respondents also occupied different administrative positions (M = 1.63, SD = 0.78), including Administrative Officers, Administrative Assistants, and Administrative Aides, providing a comprehensive assessment of the Muslim women executives from employees performing varied organizational functions. Meanwhile, relatively similar distributions were observed in highest educational attainment (M = 1.26, SD = 0.48), administrative work experience (M = 1.26, SD = 0.44), and eligibility (M = 1.20, SD = 0.44), indicating a generally comparable professional background among the respondents. In terms of employment status, the mean score of 1.72 (SD = 0.87) reflects the inclusion of employees with different employment classifications, thereby enriching the breadth of perspectives represented in the study. Overall, the demographic and professional diversity of the subordinate respondents strengthened the reliability of the data and provided a balanced evaluation of the personal competencies and work engagement of Muslim women executives. Such diversity is essential in organizational research, as it enhances the credibility and representativeness of employee perceptions regarding leadership effectiveness and workplace engagement (Northouse, 2022; Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Research Question 2: What is the level of personal competencies of Muslim Women Executives in terms of: Stress Management, Integrity, Communication, and Personal Engagement?

Table 3. Personal Competencies of MWE as perceived by themselves

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Stress Management			
1. Ability to cope with the demands of the job without excessive consumption of emotional energy.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
2. Ability to cope with the demands of the job without affecting one's own health and the work environment of others.	4.13	0.338	Competent
3. Ability to cope with the demands of the job in tense, crisis or conflict situations.	4.13	0.338	Competent
4. Ability to have good self-control, remain calm and inner balance that allows good management of those situations.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
5. Ability to recognize your own level of stress.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
6. Ability to get out of high stress quickly.	4.13	0.338	Competent
7. Ability to create a climate that supports the well-being of colleagues, monitoring their emotional state and helping them to overcome difficult circumstances.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
Average	4.53	0.36	Proficient
Integrity			
1. Ability to maintain constant behavior that gains the trust of others.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
2. Responsible and professional approach of all activities, in line with the values, strategy and mission of the organization.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
3. Compliance with applicable legislation, rules, working procedures and standards of the organization.	4.13	0.338	Competent
4. Promoting and supporting an organizational culture that sanctions unethical, illegal or abusive behaviors.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
Average	4.66	0.37	Proficient
Communication			
1. Ability and courage to express opinions pertinently, to say things by name.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
2. Ability to manage conflicts effectively and to overcome obstacle in communication.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
3. Ability to create an environment in which open debate and sincere dialogue are encourages.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
4. Ability to support clear, concise, and compelling communications for multiple audiences, both in written and in oral.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
5. Ability to actively listen to the interlocutors to identify common points in case of divergence of opinion or to identify optimal solutions to problems encountered.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
Average	4.83	0.38	Proficient
Personal Engagement			
1. Ability to generate enthusiasm and commitment among others to achieve the strategic objectives of the organization.	4.83	0.381	Proficient
2. Ability to inspire confidence in coordinated team members for the future	4.83	0.381	Proficient
3. Ability to motivate team members	4.83	0.381	Proficient
4. Ability to cultivate team performance.	4.33	0.482	Proficient
Average	4.71	0.41	Proficient

Table 3 shows that Muslim Women Executives (MWEs) demonstrated an overall proficient level of personal competency, with all dimensions obtaining mean scores within the proficient range. Among the competency dimensions, communication recorded the highest mean ($M = 4.83$, $SD = 0.38$), indicating strong communication skills essential for effective leadership and organizational performance (Northouse, 2022). This was followed by personal engagement ($M = 4.71$, $SD = 0.41$) and integrity ($M = 4.66$, $SD = 0.37$), suggesting that the respondents are highly committed to their work and uphold ethical standards in performing their duties. Meanwhile, stress management obtained the lowest mean ($M = 4.53$, $SD = 0.36$), although it remained within the proficient category, indicating that the respondents are generally capable of managing workplace pressures effectively. Overall, the consistently high mean scores and low standard deviations suggest that the Muslim women executives possess well-developed competencies necessary for effective leadership. These findings support Competency Theory, which emphasizes that leadership

effectiveness is influenced by the possession of essential skills, behaviors, and personal attributes (Boyatzis, 2018).

Table 4. Personal Competencies of MWE as perceived by their subordinates

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Stress Management			
1. Ability to cope with the demands of the job without excessive consumption of emotional energy.	4.7250	0.50147	Proficient
2. Ability to cope with the demands of the job without affecting one's own health and the work environment of others.	3.9917	0.99996	Competent
3. Ability to cope with the demands of the job in tense, crisis or conflict situations.	4.1583	0.50203	Competent
4. Ability to have good self-control, remain calm and inner balance that allows good management of those situations.	3.3667	0.75519	Advanced Beginner
5. Ability to recognize your own level of stress.	4.1667	0.37424	Competent
6. Ability to get out of high stress quickly.	3.2250	0.47567	Advanced Beginner
7. Ability to create a climate that supports the well-being of colleagues, monitoring their emotional state and helping them to overcome difficult circumstances.	3.3667	0.75519	Advanced Beginner
Average	3.8571	0.6234	Competent
Integrity			
1. Ability to maintain constant behavior that gains the trust of others.	3.3667	0.75519	Advanced Beginner
2. Responsible and professional approach of all activities, in line with the values, strategy and mission of the organization.	3.3667	0.75519	Advanced Beginner
3. Compliance with applicable legislation, rules, working procedures and standards of the organization.	3.2250	0.47567	Advanced Beginner
4. Promoting and supporting an organizational culture that sanctions unethical, illegal or abusive behaviors.	4.1667	0.37424	Competent
Average	3.5313	0.5901	Competent
Communication			
1. Ability and courage to express opinions pertinently, to say things by name.	4.1667	0.37424	Competent
2. Ability to manage conflicts effectively and to overcome obstacle in communication.	4.1667	0.37424	Competent
3. Ability to create an environment in which open debate and sincere dialogue are encourages.	4.1667	0.37424	Competent
4. Ability to support clear, concise, and compelling communications for multiple audiences, both in written and in oral.	4.1667	0.37424	Competent
5. Ability to actively listen to the interlocutors to identify common points in case of divergence of opinion or to identify optimal solutions to problems encountered.	4.1667	0.37424	Competent
Average	4.1667	0.3742	Competent
Personal Engagement			
1. Ability to generate enthusiasm and commitment among others to achieve the strategic objectives of the organization.	4.9667	0.18026	Proficient
2. Ability to inspire confidence in coordinated team members for the future	4.1667	0.37424	Competent
3. Ability to motivate team members	3.3667	0.75519	Advanced Beginner
4. Ability to cultivate team performance.	3.4000	0.80335	Advanced Beginner
Average	3.9750	0.5283	Competent

Table 4 shows that the Muslim Women Executives (MWEs) were generally perceived by their subordinates as Competent in terms of personal competencies. Among the dimensions, communication obtained the highest average mean ($M = 4.17$, $SD = 0.37$), indicating that the executives effectively communicate and maintain positive workplace relationships. This was followed by personal engagement ($M = 3.98$, $SD = 0.53$) and stress management ($M = 3.86$, $SD = 0.62$), both interpreted as competent. These

findings suggest that the executives demonstrate satisfactory levels of commitment to their work and the ability to manage workplace demands. Effective communication and engagement are important leadership competencies that contribute to organizational effectiveness and employee cooperation (Northouse, 2022). Among the dimensions, integrity obtained the lowest average mean ($M = 3.53$, $SD = 0.59$), although it remained within the competent category. Notably, several indicators under stress management and integrity were rated as Advanced Beginner, indicating areas for further improvement. Overall, the findings suggest that while the Muslim women executives possess satisfactory personal competencies, strengthening integrity and stress management may further enhance their leadership effectiveness. These results support Competency Theory, which emphasizes the continuous development of leadership skills and behaviors for improved organizational performance (Boyatzis, 2018).

Research Question 3: What is the level of employee work engagement in terms of: absorption, dedication, and vigor?

Table 5. Employee Work Engagement of MWE as perceived by themselves

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Absorption			
1. Time flies when I'm working.	4.42	0.504	Very High
2. When I am working, I forget everything else around me.	4.00	0.000	High
3. I feel happy when I am working intensely.	4.42	0.504	Very High
4. I am immersed in my work.	4.42	0.504	Very High
5. I get carried away when I'm working.	4.00	0.000	High
6. It is difficult to detach myself from my job.	4.00	0.000	High
Average	4.21	0.25	Very High
Dedication			
1. I find the work that I do full of meaning and purpose.	4.00	0.000	High
2. I am enthusiastic about my job.	4.42	0.504	Very High
3. My job inspires me.	4.42	0.504	Very High
4. I am proud of the work that I do.	4.00	0.000	High
5. To me, my job is challenging.	4.42	0.504	Very High
Average	4.25	0.30	Very High
Vigor			
1. At my work, I feel bursting with energy.	4.42	0.504	Very High
2. At my job, I feel strong and vigorous.	4.00	0.000	High
3. When I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work.	4.00	0.000	High
4. I can continue working for very long periods at a time.	4.00	0.000	High
5. At my job, I am very resilient, mentally	4.42	0.504	Very High
6. At my work I always persevere, even when things do not go well.	4.42	0.504	Very High
Average	4.21	0.25	Very High

Table 5 presents the level of employee work engagement of Muslim Women Executives (MWEs) in terms of absorption, dedication, and vigor. The findings reveal that all three dimensions were rated Very High, indicating that the respondents are highly engaged in their work. Among the dimensions, dedication obtained the highest average mean ($M = 4.25$, $SD = 0.30$), followed by absorption ($M = 4.21$, $SD = 0.25$) and vigor ($M = 4.21$, $SD = 0.25$). These results suggest that the executives are strongly committed to their work, enthusiastic about their responsibilities, and deeply involved in their organizational roles. The consistently high ratings across all dimensions indicate that the respondents demonstrate high levels of energy, persistence, concentration, and commitment in performing their duties. The relatively low standard deviations further suggest a high degree of agreement among the respondents regarding their work engagement. These findings support the Work Engagement Theory of Schaufeli and Bakker (2004), which posits that engaged employees exhibit vigor, dedication, and absorption, resulting in greater motivation, productivity, and organizational effectiveness. Overall, the results indicate that Muslim women executives in Tawi-Tawi maintain a strong psychological connection to their work and are highly committed to achieving organizational goals.

Table 6. Employee Work Engagement as perceived by their subordinates

Statement	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Absorption			
1. Time flies when I'm working.	3.9500	0.92446	High
2. When I am working, I forget everything else around me.	4.3167	0.67343	Very High
3. I feel happy when I am working intensely.	4.5500	0.56286	Very High
4. I am immersed in my work.	4.5750	0.51306	Very High
5. I get carried away when I'm working.	4.5750	0.51306	Very High
6. It is difficult to detach myself from my job.	4.1500	0.38128	High
Average	4.3528	0.5947	Very High
Dedication			
1. I find the work that I do full of meaning and purpose.	4.7583	0.44901	Very High
2. I am enthusiastic about my job.	4.9333	0.31042	Very High
3. My job inspires me.	4.6250	0.58068	Very High
4. I am proud of the work that I do.	3.9750	0.95673	High
5. To me, my job is challenging.	4.5000	0.55002	Very High
Average	4.5583	0.5694	Very High
Vigor			
1. At my work, I feel bursting with energy.	4.6667	0.53974	Very High
2. At my job, I feel strong and vigorous.	4.4000	0.54077	Very High
3. When I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work.	4.7167	0.50516	Very High
4. I can continue working for very long periods at a time.	4.2917	0.50868	Very High
5. At my job, I am very resilient, mentally	4.9500	0.31356	Very High
6. At my work I always persevere, even when things do not go well.	4.9500	0.31356	Very High
Average	4.6625	0.4536	Very High

Table 6 presents the level of employee work engagement of Muslim Women Executives (MWEs) as perceived by their subordinates in terms of absorption, dedication, and vigor. The findings reveal that all three dimensions were rated Very High, indicating that the executives are highly engaged in their work. Among the dimensions, vigor obtained the highest average mean ($M = 4.66$, $SD = 0.45$), followed by dedication ($M = 4.56$, $SD = 0.57$) and absorption ($M = 4.35$, $SD = 0.59$). These results suggest that the executives demonstrate high levels of energy, resilience, enthusiasm, and commitment in carrying out their responsibilities. The consistently high ratings across all dimensions indicate that the subordinates perceive the executives as highly motivated, persistent, and deeply involved in their work. Notably, several indicators under vigor received exceptionally high ratings, including V5 and V6 ($M = 4.95$), reflecting strong perceptions of enthusiasm and perseverance. The relatively low standard deviations further indicate consistency in the respondents' assessments. These findings support the Work Engagement Theory of Schaufeli and Bakker (2004), which posits that engaged employees exhibit vigor, dedication, and absorption, leading to enhanced individual and organizational performance. Overall, the results suggest that Muslim women executives in Tawi-Tawi are viewed by their subordinates as highly committed leaders who actively contribute to organizational effectiveness and goal attainment.

Research Question 4: Are there significant differences in personal competencies and work engagement when respondents are grouped according to profile variables?

Table 7. Mann Whitney U Test Results for the Differences in MWE Work Engagement, and Personal Competency According to Respondents' Profiles

Category	Mean Rank	U	Z	Asympt. Sig.	Decision	Interpretation
Work Engagement						
Age		46.500	-.538	.591	Accept Ho	Not Significant
45 years old & below	13.75					
Above 45 yrs old	12.08					
Highest Educ. Attainment		63.500	-.033	.974	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Master's Degree	12.53					
Doctorate Degree	12.44					
Admin. Work Exp		78.000	.504	.614	Accept Ho	Not Significant
20 yrs & below	11.93					
Above 20 yrs	13.30					
Personal Competency						
Age		75.00	1.454	.146	Accept Ho	Not Significant
45 years old & below	9.00					
Above 45 yrs old	13.67					
Highest Educ. Attainment		69.000	.318	.750	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Master's Degree	12.19					
Doctorate Degree	13.12					
Admin. Work Exp		91.500	1.308	.191	Accept Ho	Not Significant
20 yrs & below	10.96					
Above 20 yrs	14.66					

Table 7 presents the results of the Mann–Whitney U Test examining differences in work engagement and personal competency among Muslim Women Executives (MWEs) based on age, highest educational attainment, and administrative work experience. The findings revealed no significant differences in work engagement according to age ($p = .591$), educational attainment ($p = .974$), and administrative work experience ($p = .614$), as all p -values exceeded the .05 level of significance. This indicates that the respondents demonstrated similar levels of vigor, dedication, and absorption regardless of their demographic and professional characteristics (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Likewise, no significant differences were found in personal competency according to age ($p = .146$), educational attainment ($p = .750$), and administrative work experience ($p = .191$). The results suggest that the respondents possessed comparable levels of stress management, integrity, communication, and personal engagement regardless of their profiles. Overall, the findings indicate that the Muslim women executives exhibited consistently high levels of personal competency and work engagement, irrespective of age, educational attainment, and administrative experience (Boyatzis, 2018).

Table 8. Kruskal Wallis H Test Results for the Differences in MWE Work Engagement, and Personal Competency According to Respondents' Profiles

Category	Mean Rank	X ²	df	Sig.	Decision	Interpretation
Work Engagement						
Current Position		.063	2	.969	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Provincial Director	12.33					
Provincial Head	12.38					
Manager	13.25					
Appointment Status		.404	2	.817	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Permanent/Regular	12.92					
Probationary	9.75					
Designated	12.50					
Eligibility		.430	2	.807	Accept Ho	Not Significant
CS Professional	12.56					
PRC (RA1080)	13.25					
CESO/CSWE	9.75					
Personal Competency						
Current Position		.727	2	.695	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Provincial Director	11.42					
Provincial Head	14.06					
Manager	12.62					
Appointment Status		.938	2	.626	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Permanent/Regular	11.27					
Probationary	13.50					
Designated	14.06					
Eligibility		2.421	2	.298	Accept Ho	Not Significant
CS Professional	11.00					
PRC (RA1080)	15.08					
CESO/CSWE	16.75					

Table 8 presents the results of the Kruskal–Wallis H Test conducted to determine whether significant differences exist in the levels of work engagement and personal competency among Muslim Women Executives (MWEs) when grouped according to current position, appointment status, and eligibility. The findings revealed that all computed p-values were greater than the .05 level of significance, resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis in all cases. For work engagement, no significant differences were found according to current position ($\chi^2 = 0.063$, $p = .969$), appointment status ($\chi^2 = 0.404$, $p = .817$), and eligibility ($\chi^2 = 0.430$, $p = .807$). Likewise, personal competency did not significantly differ according to current position ($\chi^2 = 0.727$, $p = .695$), appointment status ($\chi^2 = 0.938$, $p = .626$), and eligibility ($\chi^2 = 2.421$, $p = .298$). Although slight variations in mean ranks were observed among the groups, these differences were not statistically significant. The findings indicate that Muslim women executives demonstrated comparable levels of work engagement and personal competency regardless of their position, employment status, and professional eligibility. This suggests that leadership effectiveness, commitment to work, and personal competencies are consistently manifested across the respondents, irrespective of their professional classifications. The results support the view that work engagement and competencies are developed through professional experience and organizational involvement rather than position or credentials alone (Boyatzis, 2018; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004).

Research Question 5: Is there a significant relationship between personal competencies and employee work engagement?

Table 9. Spearman rho Results for the Test of Relationship Among Variables

Variables	Spearman's rho	P value	Decision	Interpretation
Personal Competency and Work Engagement	.023	.914	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 9 shows the results of the Spearman rho correlation analysis between personal competency and work engagement among Muslim Women Executives (MWEs). The analysis revealed a very weak positive correlation ($\rho = .023$) that was not statistically significant ($p = .914$). Since the p-value exceeded the .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating that no significant relationship exists between personal competency and work engagement. This finding suggests that although the respondents demonstrated Proficient personal competencies and Very High work engagement, improvements in one variable were not associated with increases in the other. The result implies that work engagement may be influenced by factors beyond personal competencies, such as organizational support, work environment, and job resources (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). Therefore, personal competency and work engagement appear to operate independently among Muslim women executives in Tawi-Tawi.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical principles were strictly observed throughout the conduct of this study to safeguard the rights, welfare, privacy, and dignity of all participants. Prior to data collection, ethical clearance was secured from the Research Ethics Committee of the Graduate School of Zamboanga Peninsula Polytechnic State University (ZPPSU). Formal permission to conduct the study was likewise obtained from the Regional and Provincial Offices of the participating government agencies and public institutions in the Province of Tawi-Tawi through approved letters of request. Before administering the survey questionnaire, the researcher provided participants with an informed consent form explaining the purpose of the study, research procedures, expected duration of participation, potential risks and benefits, confidentiality measures, and participants' rights. Participation was entirely voluntary, and participants were informed that they could refuse participation or withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or adverse consequences. Only those who voluntarily signed the informed consent form were included in the study. To ensure confidentiality and anonymity, participants were not required to provide names or any personally identifiable information. Unique codes were assigned to questionnaires for data management purposes. All completed questionnaires and electronic data files were stored in password-protected devices and secured storage folders accessible only to the researcher. Hard-copy documents were kept in a locked cabinet during the research process. Data will be retained for a period consistent with institutional research policies and will thereafter be securely destroyed through shredding of paper records and permanent deletion of electronic files. Considering the cultural and religious context of the study, special attention was given to respecting the values, beliefs, traditions, and sensitivities of the Muslim women executives and their subordinate employees. All interactions were conducted with professionalism, cultural sensitivity, and respect. Furthermore, the study adhered to the principles of beneficence, respect for persons, justice, honesty, and integrity by ensuring that all data were accurately collected, analyzed, interpreted, and reported without fabrication, falsification, or misrepresentation.

Conclusion

The study concluded that Muslim women executives in Tawi-Tawi demonstrated proficient personal competencies and a very high level of work engagement. They were particularly strong in communication, vigor, dedication, and absorption, reflecting their commitment to their leadership roles and organizational responsibilities. It further showed no significant differences in personal competencies and work engagement across demographic and professional characteristics. Likewise, no significant relationship was found between personal competencies and work engagement, suggesting that employee engagement may be influenced by other organizational and contextual factors beyond individual competencies. Overall, the results highlight the leadership capability and strong professional engagement

of Muslim women executives in Tawi-Tawi which contributed to a better understanding of women's leadership and employee engagement within the local public-sector context.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that Muslim women executives continue to participate in leadership and professional development programs that further enhance their competencies in stress management, integrity, communication, and personal engagement. Organizations should likewise sustain and strengthen initiatives that promote employee work engagement through recognition programs, mentoring opportunities, wellness activities, and continuous professional development. Given that communication emerged as the strongest competency dimension, Muslim women executives may be encouraged to serve as mentors and role models in leadership development programs to help cultivate future women leaders within their organizations. Furthermore, since no significant differences were found across demographic and professional profile variables, leadership and engagement enhancement programs may be implemented uniformly to ensure equal opportunities for growth and development among executives. Considering that no significant relationship was established between personal competencies and work engagement, organizational leaders should explore other factors that may influence employee engagement, such as organizational culture, leadership support, job satisfaction, work-life balance, and workplace climate. Future researchers are encouraged to replicate this study in other organizational settings using larger samples and to investigate additional variables that may contribute to work engagement and leadership effectiveness. Qualitative and mixed-method approaches may also be employed to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences and challenges of Muslim women executives in diverse organizational contexts.

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